

THE ROLE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING STUDENTS TO LITERACY AND SPEECH DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *In this article, the role of pedagogical technologies in the development of speech in literacy training in elementary grades, the shortcomings of the student's speech in the period of literacy are discussed in this article. reasons are explained.*

Keywords: *point, methodology, literacy, pronunciation standards, ped technology.*

In our country, spiritual education has been raised to the level of state policy of well-rounded human education. Because man is the backbone of society. It is not for nothing that our head of state said: "A perfect generation is the foundation of Uzbekistan's development." Because the personality of each student can dramatically influence the development of the future. The correct development of speech is of great importance for every child who receives education and upbringing to become a fully formed person based on the needs of the times and actively participate in the affairs of society.

Speech is a means of communication between people, a national wealth and a powerful tool for obtaining the necessary knowledge. Therefore, it is important for everyone to learn to master speech and to fully express their thoughts.

Correct and fluent speech is of great importance in teaching students to read. Proper training of preschool children's speech for primary education requires in-depth knowledge and skills from the primary school teacher. The child lives in the processes of practical application of the mother tongue even at preschool age. The existing language environment forms the child's initial skills and competencies related to the practical use of his language. The role of pronunciation in the process of speaking is huge. Pronunciation norms are the leading factor in the formation of the form of oral speech. Because the preservation of uniformity in terms of sound in the process of speaking is primarily explained by the uniformity of pronunciation norms.

In fact, the child pronounces words in his mother tongue for the first time. Vocabulary increases with age. Basically, the correct form of speech is formed and developed in primary grades.

Ignored defects in the child's speech at preschool age will cause the child to lag behind in getting proper education at school in the future. Among children who are developing according to the norm of speech, it helps children of preschool age to fully develop fluent speech.

The role of ped technologies in the development of speech in the teaching of literacy in primary grades is incomparable. The lesson is the most delicate point, the foundation of the educational process. One of the criteria for improving the effectiveness of the lesson is the use of ped technologies in one of the lessons.

To improve the educational content and educational efficiency, to improve the educational content and educational efficiency, and to eliminate the shortcomings in the students' speech, using

pedagogical technologies in regular classes to teach literacy and develop their oral and written speech. So, the aspects that we should pay attention to when developing speech are as follows:

1. being able to choose the right methods in the process of speech development;
2. continuous reading of works of art;
3. working with texts encouraging logical thinking;
4. organization of various competition classes;
5. encourage students to memorize many poems;
6. writing statements, impressions
7. call to create creative works;

The reasons for the student's speech deficits during the literacy period are as follows:

- ✓ lack of pre-school education;
- ✓ lack of development at the level of thinking;
- ✓ lack of education in the mother tongue;

It is appropriate to use such non-traditional technologies in the cultivation of speech:

- Seven steps;
- Sinkwain
- Insert;
- Problematic situation;
- Stairs-stairs
- Charxpalak;
- Exhibition of cubes;
- Venn diagram;
- Collage;
- Mental attack;

In order to develop students' oral speech, the following activities are carried out in cooperation with parents:

- In the interpretation of TV shows;
- Communication;
- Extracurricular activities;
- Working with family and parents;
- Reading books;
- Work on the text;

In fact, the above-mentioned ped technologies serve to improve students' knowledge-efficiency and fluency in speech.

Including:

1. "Everyone teaches everyone" technology. This technology is used to strengthen the knowledge of 3-4 graders about word groups and to develop their oral speech. Students are divided into 4 groups. Each group will say in one sentence its rule related to one-word group. For example, who is a horse? what? who are what are there will be an answer to the question. All the students in the group say in turn the rules that are the answer to the noun phrase.

2. "A thousand children of one mother" technology. The use of technology is used in classes of primary grades (1, 2, 3, 4). The student is instructed to find an unfamiliar new word from the letters (for example HELP)

- In 1st grades: find words that start with a letter;
- In 2nd grades: find words starting with the letter k and ending with the letter k;
- In 3rd grades: find words beginning with the letter k in the middle ending with the letter k;
- In 4th grades: you are instructed to find words whose letter is a double consonant in the middle of the word.

In addition, from 3-4 grades, this technology is used to find words with the same meaning and to find words with the opposite meaning. This is the advantage of technology; develops students' oral and written speech. Increases vocabulary. Another good thing is that students' progress step by step from simple to complex.

- Grades 1 key, ball, ship, partridge, sunflower, sesame, blue.
- 2 classes: blue, cake, ball, deer, need, cut, rainbow, maid.
- 3 classes: partridge, lizard, woodpecker, blue - blue, breast.
- 4 classes: sly, clever, clever, hack, mack, two, accordion.

The methods largely depend on the age characteristics of the students. As children grow older, the level of independent work on language materials also increases. Therefore, when choosing a text, whether it is oral or written, it is important to choose the appropriate age and worldview of the student, creative thinking method also gives good results in developing students' speech. In this, attention is mainly paid to the choice of a didactic topic.

A fluent student can easily express his opinion in front of many people on any topic. Therefore, the issue of speech development remains one of the most relevant aspects of mother tongue education.

After all, in the process of preparation for PISA and PERLS tests at the international level, students' logical thinking is mainly taken into account. The effectiveness of the use of these pedagogic technologies, the development of students' speech is of particular importance in the current situation, where the education of free-thinking individuals has become a priority of the state policy. Speech development has become a necessary condition for personality formation.

Therefore, the development of oral and written speech in primary education is important in raising a civilized, perfect person in society. As our grandfather Navoi used to say: "A word is a gem." We should treat it with respect. We need to understand its meaning and explain it to our children. So that this unique native language of ours does not lose its charm and lives forever.

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